

ASSESSMENT OF IRON STATUS AS A PREDICTOR OF GESTATIONAL DIABETES MELLITUS

Duaa Jassim Kut

Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Tikrit Teaching Hospital, Tikrit, Iraq

Sarab Salih Jasim

Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Tikrit University-College of Medicine, Tikrit, Iraq

Abstract: This a comparative prospective study was conducted from 1st of October 2023 to 30th June 2024 in Tikrit teaching hospital department of obstetrics and gynecology. A convenient sample of 50 pregnant women with the risk factors of the gestational diabetes mellitus (Group A), and 50 women without risk factors of gestational diabetes mellitus (Group B) were enrolled from the 1st trimester of pregnancy and followed every 3 month for the development of the gestational diabetes. The incidence of gestational diabetes that developed among the whole was 15(15%), among (Group A) significantly had higher incidence of gestational diabetes 11(22%), than (Group B) 4 (8%). The gestational diabetes patient most of them significantly had had S. ferritin level of (> 44.5 mg/L) 8(53.3%), followed by (24-44.5 mg/L) 5(33.3%), higher than those who hadn't GDM 17(20%), and 19(22.4%), respectively. Serum ferritin Significantly associated with body mass index ≥ 25 (kg/m²) 18(51.4 %), aged ≥ 40 years 3(75%), had Previous history of gestational diabetes 3(27.3 %), had history of newborn's macrosomia (≥ 4500 g) 12(92.3 %) and family history of type 1 or 2 diabetes in first-degree or second-degree relatives 10 (58.8 %). Those who had s. ferritin Q4 (> 44.5 mg/L) in 1st trimester significantly had higher mean of HbA1c 4.6 ± 0.78 , higher mean of fasting Blood Sugar (mg/dL) 87.24 ± 3.94 in 1st trimester higher mean of fasting Blood Sugar (mg/dL) in the 2nd trimester 94.12 ± 12.14 and higher mean of weight gain 3.48 ± 0.67 .

Keywords: Iron and GDM, Iron as a Predictor of GDM.

INTRODUCTION

Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) is defined as “any degree of glucose intolerance occurring first time during pregnancy”. [1,2] With the global increase in obesity, GDM prevalence has also increased. There is a variable range of incidence in all pregnancies starting from 1 to 14% that are complicated by gestational diabetes mellitus [3]. The global prevalence of GDM has increased and it is considered to affect up to 15–20% of all pregnancies. [4,5] The most common complications are congenital malformations, stillbirth or neonatal death, macrosomia, in utero growth retardation, shoulder dystocia, neonatal hypoglycemia, and neonatal respiratory distress, which may lead to admission to a neonatal intensive care unit [6]. Thus, preventing GDM is essential and imperative for improving the health quality of population. Iron is especially important in pregnant women to meet the high requirements and iron deficiency is the most prevalent nutritional deficiency worldwide. During pregnancy, iron deficiency is associated with multiple adverse outcomes for both mother and child, including increased risk of bleeding, sepsis, maternal mortality,

perinatal mortality and low birth weight [7] Hemoglobin (Hb) measurement, an indicator of nutritional status, is routinely tested during perinatal visit. anemia is often easy to be concerned. However, high maternal hemoglobin has not been paid enough attention to, because it has long been regarded as a good signal. But several studies have shown that high hemoglobin levels during pregnancy are associated with many pregnancy complications [8,9] However, the relationship between hemoglobin levels and GDM has been poorly studied, especially focusing on hemoglobin levels in different trimesters of pregnancy. Oxidative stress induced by iron overload can gradually damage the function of islet cells and lead to disorder of glucose metabolism [10]. It is still needed to clarify the relative risk of iron status and gestational diabetes. The aim of this study aimed to assess the relationship between elevated iron status, measured as hemoglobin and ferritin levels and the risk of gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM).

MATERIAL

This a comparative prospective study was conducted from 1st of October 2023 to 30th June 2024 in Tikrit teaching hospital department of obstetrics and gynecology. A convenient sample of 50 pregnant women with the risk factors of the gestational diabetes mellitus (Group A), and 50 women without risk factors of gestational diabetes mellitus (Group B) were enrolled from the 1st trimester of pregnancy and followed every 3 month for the development of the gestational diabetes.

Inclusion Criteria include: Singleton pregnant women aged 18–40 years in their 1st trimester of gestation and had at least one of the following risk factors: BMI ≥ 25 kg/m²; Age ≥ 40 years, Previously had gestational diabetes, Glucose intolerance or newborn's macrosomia (≥ 4500 g) in any earlier pregnancy or type 1 or 2 diabetes in first-degree or second-degree relatives. Women those excluded include: An abnormal glucose measurement in (8–12 weeks' gestation), pre-pregnancy diabetes, age < 18 years, multiple pregnancy, substance abuse or psychiatric illness, and reluctance to participate in the study.

RESULTS

Most of the cases group was in age group of 30-35 years 18(36%), in comparison to control group 15(30%). Most of the cases group was in urban areas 32(64%), in comparison to control group 29(58%). Most of the cases group had 1ry educational level 18(36%), in comparison to control group 11(22%). All of the cases group had housewife job 50(100%), in comparison to control group 46(92%). All the above were of statistically none significant relation as shown in table 1. Most of the cases group had BMI of 25-29.9 (kg/m²) 26(52%), followed by ≥ 30 (kg/m²) 9 (18%), in comparison to 0(0%) of the control group, in statistically significant relation, as shown in table 1. The incidence of GDM that developed among the whole was 15(15%), as shown in figure 1. Among the control group the incidence of GDM was 4(8%), while among the study group (those with risk factor of GDM) was 11(22%), this relation was statistically significant (P value < 0.05), as shown in figure 2. The GDM patient most of them had had S. ferritin level of (> 44.5 mg/L) 8(53.3%), followed by (24-44.5 mg/L)5(33.3%), in comparison to those who hadn't GDM 17(20%), and 19(22.4%), respectively, this relation was statically significant as shown in table 2. Most of the women who had BMI ≥ 25 (kg/m²) had s. ferritin (> 44.5 mg/L) had 18(51.4 %) in comparison to 7(10.8%) of those had BMI < 25 (kg/m²). Most of the women who aged ≥ 40 years had s. ferritin (> 44.5 mg/L) 3(75%) in comparison to 22(22.9%) of those aged < 40 years. All the above were of statistically none significant relations as shown in table 3.

Previous history of GDM who had s. ferritin (> 44.5 mg/L) was 3(27.3 %) in comparison to 22(24.7%) of those hadn't GDM. Previous history of newborn's macrosomia (≥ 4500 g) who had s. ferritin (> 44.5 mg/L) was 12(92.3 %) in comparison to 13(14.9 %) of those hadn't history of newborn's macrosomia. Previous history of type 1 or 2 diabetes in first-degree or second-degree relatives who had s. ferritin (> 44.5 mg/L) 10 (58.8 %) was significantly higher than o 15 of those who hadn't (18.1%). All the above were of statistically significant relations as shown in table 3.

The mean BMI among those had s. ferritin (> 44.5 mg/L) was 25.99 ± 5.34 in comparison to those in Q1 S. ferritin 23.93 ± 2.65 . The mean Hb among those had s. ferritin (> 44.5 mg/L) was 12.3 ± 1.8 in comparison to those in Q1 S. ferritin 9.96 ± 1.8 . The mean HbA1c among those had s. ferritin (> 44.5 mg/L) was 4.6 ± 0.78 in comparison to those in Q1 S. ferritin 4.13 ± 0.56 . The mean Random Blood Sugar (mg/dL) 1st trimester among those had s. ferritin (> 44.5 mg/L) was 109.08 ± 9.27 in comparison to those in Q1 S. ferritin 95.04 ± 8.22 . The mean fasting Blood Sugar (mg/dL) in 1st trimester among those had s. ferritin (> 44.5 mg/L) was 87.24 ± 3.94 in comparison to those in Q1 S. ferritin 74.40 ± 10.94 . The mean fasting Blood Sugar (mg/dL) in 2nd trimester among those had s. ferritin (> 44.5 mg/L) was 94.12 ± 12.14 in comparison to those in Q1 S. ferritin 88.28 ± 8.64 . The mean Weight gain from pre pregnancy to 2nd trimester in (kg) among those had s. ferritin (> 44.5 mg/L) was 3.48 ± 0.67 in comparison to those in Q1 S. ferritin 2.24 ± 1.42 . All the above were of statistically significant relations as shown in table 4.

DISCUSSION

The current study reported the incidence of GDM that developed among the whole was 15(15%), while among cases group (those with risk factor of GDM) significantly had higher incidence of GDM 11(22%), than control group 4(8%). This goes with Agarwal MM in 2020 in California worked on GDM in Arab countries who found that the prevalence of GDM (5.1–37.7%) in countries of the Arab Gulf are amongst the highest internationally, and they are still rising precipitously. [11] This is also in concordance with Li G et al [12] in 2020 in China, who found that the incidence and age-adjusted incidence of GDM in Qingdao were 17.42 and 17.45%. This finding also goes with what found in Salah Al-Deen governorate by Mohammed MK [13] that 13.33% of the sample having GDM. The lower rate was because the take the general population not taking in consecration population with GDM risk factors. The cause of high rate of GDM in Iraq and Arab region is related to the changes in lifestyle, due to the sudden prosperity, contributed to a marked rise in obesity [14], better living standards, increased urbanization, increased calorie intake, as well as decreased exercise due to reliance on cars and migrant workers. [15]

Another important factor that may have contributed to the increased prevalence of T2DM in the Arabic-speaking countries is the highly prevalent consanguinity, which could help to cluster the genes shared between GDM and T2DM [16].

The GDM patient most of them significantly had had S. ferritin level of (> 44.5 mg/L) 8(53.3%), followed by (24-44.5 mg/L) 5(33.3%), higher than those who hadn't GDM 17(20%), and 19(22.4%), respectively. This goes with Zhang X et al [17] 2021 in China, who found that the adjusted RRs (95% CIs) of GDM across the increasing quartiles of plasma ferritin concentrations were, Q2 = 2.14 (1.37, 3.34), Q3=2.03 (1.30, 3.19), and Q4= 2.72 (1.76, 4.21), respectively (P-value < 0.01). Cheng Y et al [18] in 2020 in China, found that the incidence of GDM was significantly elevated in women in the higher quartiles of serum ferritin (Q3 and Q4), 18.8%, and 19.3%, respectively. Amiri et al.'s study in 2013 in Iran, showed that high ferritin levels (greater than 80 $\mu\text{g/L}$) increased the risk of gestational diabetes by 2.4-fold (95% CI: 0.83–6.9, P = 0.10), while in the group with ferritin levels below 20 $\mu\text{g/L}$, the risk of GDM was reduced by 82% (OR: 0.8, 95% CI: 0.08–0.37, P = 0.001) [19].

Khambalia AZ et al [20] in 2016 in Australia found that increased odds of gestational diabetes with increasing s. ferritin level (OR 1.41; 95% CI 1.11, 1.78).

The positive association between plasma ferritin concentrations and GDM also found by Rawal S [21] in 2017 in USA, and Zein S et al [22] in 2015 in Lebanon, but they take diabetic patient and tested the s. ferritin for them. In current study a significantly higher proportion of women who had BMI ≥ 25 (kg/m²) had s. ferritin (> 44.5 mg/L) 18(51.4 %) in comparison to 7(10.8%) of those who had BMI < 25 (kg/m²) was found. This goes with Bowers KA et al [23] in 2016 in Danish, found that women with GDM had a higher BMI (28.76 ± 6.0) compared with controls (24.16 ± 4.6). Cheng Y et al [18] in 2020 in China, found that in

Q4, pregnant women with a pre-pregnancy body mass index ≥ 24 kg/m². Significantly higher proportion of women who aged ≥ 40 years had s. ferritin (> 44.5 mg/L) 3(75%) in comparison to 22(22.9%) of those aged < 40 years. This goes with Zhang X et al [17] 2021 in China, who found that the mean age of mothers lie in Q4 (≥ 90.0 ng/mL) of S.ferritin level (28.1 ± 3.1) was higher than those in Q1 (≤ 29.5 ng/mL) with mean age (27.6 ± 3.2). Cheng Y et al [18] in 2020 in China found none significant having high s. ferritin with increasing age (30.27 ± 3.20) (30.16 ± 3.31), for Q4, and Q1 respectively.

The two previous studies not taking in consecration that the risk of GDM is age > 40 years as we do, therefore their mean of age was lower than reported in this study.

Previous history of type 1 or 2 diabetes in first-degree or second-degree relatives who had s. ferritin (> 44.5 mg/L) 10 (58.8 %) was significantly higher than o 15 of those who hadn't (18.1%). This goes with Bowers KA et al [23] Bowers found that women with GDM had a higher percentage of having family history of DM (28%) in comparison to controls (8%).

Those who had s. ferritin Q4 (> 44.5 mg/L) in 1st trimester significantly had higher mean of HbA1c 4.6 ± 0.78 in comparison to those in Q1 S. ferritin 4.13 ± 0.56 . This goes with Zhang Z et al [24] in 2023 in China, found that the mean HbA1c of Q4 (5.15 ± 0.35) was significantly higher than the other groups (5.14 ± 0.38 , 5.10 ± 0.33 , 5.11 ± 0.34). This was in contrary with Cheng Y et al [18] in 2020 in China found the HbA1c at 24–28 gestational weeks decreased when serum ferritin increased ($4.49 \pm 0.42\%$, $4.41 \pm 0.35\%$, $4.32 \pm 0.33\%$ and $4.29 \pm 0.34\%$, $P < 0.001$). Those who had s. ferritin Q4 (> 44.5 mg/L) in 1st trimester significantly had higher mean of fasting Blood Sugar (mg/dL) 87.24 ± 3.94 in 1st trimester than those in Q1 S. ferritin 74.40 ± 10.94 . This goes with Zhang Z et al [24] in 2023 in China, found that the mean value of FBG of Q4 (4.90 ± 0.55) was statistically significantly higher than Q1 (4.75 ± 0.48), Q2 (4.72 ± 0.42) and Q3 (4.79 ± 0.44).

The consistency between studies indicates a positive dose-response association between circulating ferritin concentrations and GDM persisting in various populations. However, it has been noted that increasing the body's iron store contributes to increased free radical formation and oxidative stress which can result in cell damage leading to oxidative injury to pancreatic cells. Furthermore, growing insulin resistance and elevated insulin secretion from the pancreas could cause pancreatic beta-cell exhaustion [25]. Some other researches have revealed that high plasma ferritin mirrors increased iron stores of the body and might be taken as an acute phase inflammatory reactant [26]. Besides, increased plasma ferritin levels motivate the inflammatory process inducing elevated insulin resistance, decreased insulin secretion by the pancreas, and hepatic dysfunction. Ultimately it follows reduced glucose uptake by muscles and mounting gluconeogenesis, hence spelling the development of GDM [27].

CONCLUSION

Healthcare professionals should consider including serum ferritin, and HBA1c in the evaluation and monitoring of gestational diabetes in the 1st and 2nd trimester. Further researches are needed to validate these findings in larger and more diverse populations. Further studies regarding iron supplementation and gestational diabetes are needed, to be used in gestational diabetes prevention programs.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

[No any financial interest or any conflict of interest exists.]

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I wish to express my deep gratitude and sincere thanks to dean of college of medicine, and I would like to present my great gratitude to my all teaching staff members of the Obstetrics and Gynecology Committee,

for their effort during my training period. I am particularly grateful to the health care workers, and patients who participated in this study for their willingness to assist by giving me their time and information.

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TABLES

Table 1: Characteristics of Women with GDM the Control Groups

General characteristics		Control		Cases		Total		P value
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	
Age	< 25 years	15	30.0%	10	20.0%	25	25.0%	> 0.05
	25-30 years	14	28.0%	13	26.0%	27	27.0%	
	30-35 years	15	30.0%	16	32.0%	31	31.0%	
	> 35 years	6	12.0%	11	22.0%	17	17.0%	
Residence	Rural	21	42.0%	18	36.0%	39	39.0%	> 0.05
	Urban	29	58.0%	32	64.0%	61	61.0%	
Mother education	illiterate	16	32.0%	6	12.0%	22	22.0%	> 0.05
	read & write	13	26.0%	10	20.0%	23	23.0%	
	1ry school	11	22.0%	18	36.0%	29	29.0%	
	2ndry school	7	14.0%	12	24.0%	19	19.0%	

	college	3	6.0%	4	8.0%	7	7.0%	
Mother Job	Housewife	46	92.0%	50	100.0%	96	96.0%	> 0.05
	Employer	4	8.0%	0	0.0%	4	4.0%	
BMI	<18.5 (kg/m ²)	4	8.00%	0	0.00%	4	4.00%	< 0.05*
	18.5-24.9 (kg/m ²)	46	92.00%	15	30.00%	61	61.00%	
	25-29.9 (kg/m ²)	0	0.00%	26	52.00%	26	26.00%	
	≥ 30 (kg/m ²)	0	0.00%	9	18.00%	9	9.00%	
Total		50	100.00%	50	100.00%	100	100.00%	

*significant

Table 2. The Relation of Serum Ferritin Quartiles at 1st Trimester and GDM.

	S. Ferritin 1st trimester							
	Q1 (< 18.5 mg/L)		Q2 (18.5- 24 mg/L)		Q3 (24-44.5 mg/L)		Q4 (> 44.5 mg/L)	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
GDM	1	6.7%	1	6.7%	5	33.3%	8	53.3%
Non GDM	24	28.2%	25	29.4%	19	22.4%	17	20.0%
Total	25	25.0%	26	26.0%	24	24.0%	25	25.0%
P value < 0.05 significant								

Table 3. Relation of Serum Ferritin Quartiles at 1st Trimester, and GDM Risk Factors.

Risk factors	S. Ferritin 1st trimester							
	Q1(< 18.5 mg/L)		Q2 (18.5- 24 mg/L)		Q3 (24-44.5 mg/L)		Q4 (> 44.5 mg/L)	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
BMI (kg/m ²) (< 0.05)*								
<25(kg/m ²)	19	29.2%	26	40.0%	13	20.0%	7	10.8%
≥25(kg/m ²)	6	17.1%	0	0.0%	11	31.4%	18	51.4%
Age ≥40 years (> 0.05)								
Yes	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	1	25.0%	3	75.0%
No	25	26.0%	26	27.1%	23	24.0%	22	22.9%
previously GDM								
Yes	0	0.00%	6	54.5%	2	18.2%	3	27.3%
No	25	28.1%	20	22.5%	22	24.7%	22	24.7%
newborn's macrosomia (≥4500 g) (< 0.05)*								
Yes	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	1	7.7%	12	92.3%
No	25	28.7%	26	29.9%	23	26.4%	13	14.9%
type 1 or 2 diabetes in first-degree or second-degree relatives (< 0.05)*								
Yes	6	35.3%	0	0.00%	1	5.9%	10	58.8%
No	19	22.9%	26	31.3%	23	27.7%	15	18.1%
Total	25	25.0%	26	26.0%	24	24.0%	25	25.0%

*significant

Table 4. Relation of Serum Ferritin Quartiles at 1st Trimester, and Diabetes Related Factors.

Diabetes mellitus related factors	S. Ferritin 1st trimester								P value
	Q1 (< 18.5 mg/L)		Q2 ($18.5- 24$ mg/L)		Q3 ($24-44.5$ mg/L)		Q4 (> 44.5 mg/L)		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Age	32.04	4.34	28.92	6.60	27.42	6.29	29.40	8.15	>0.05
Gestational age	12.56	0.51	11.73	0.78	11.83	0.76	12.54	0.59	$<0.05^*$
BMI	23.93	2.65	22.62	2.06	25.25	4.55	25.99	5.34	$<0.05^*$
Hemoglobin	9.96	1.8	9.7	1.2	10.8	0.7	12.3	1.8	$<0.05^*$
HbA1c	4.13	0.56	4.62	0.29	4.13	0.94	4.60	0.78	$<0.05^*$
Random Blood Sugar (mg/dL) 1st trimester	95.04	8.22	103.12	11.09	97.92	14.81	109.08	9.27	$<0.05^*$
Random Blood Sugar (mg/dL) 2nd trimester	110.76	23.56	105.92	22.48	114.69	24.48	130.00	50.76	>0.05
FBG 1st trimester	74.40	10.94	83.42	7.45	80.63	8.57	87.24	3.94	$<0.05^*$
FBG 2nd trimester	88.28	8.64	85.31	10.03	89.88	10.93	94.12	12.14	$<0.05^*$
Weight gain from pre pregnancy to 2nd trimester (kg)	2.24	1.42	3.03	0.59	4.69	2.23	3.48	0.67	$<0.05^*$

SD= Standard deviation, *=significant.

FIGURES

Figure 1. The Proportion of GDM in all the Sample

Figure 2. The Proportion of GDM among Study Groups